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DEPENDENCE OF THE TWO-DIMENSIONAL COMBINED DENSITY OF STATES ON THE ABSORBING PHOTON ENERGY IN GaAs/AlGaAs AT QUANTIZING MAGNETIC FIELD

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Abstract:

Objective. The influence of the two-dimensional density of states on the oscillations of the transverse electrical conductivity in heterostructures with rectangular quantum wells is studied. A new analytical expression is derived for calculating the temperature dependence of the oscillations of the transverse electrical conductivity and magnetoresistance of a quantum well.

Methods. Oscillations of the electrical conductivity and magnetoresistance of a narrow-window quantum well with a nonparabolic dispersion law are studied. The proposed theory was used to study the results of experiments on a narrow-gap quantum well ($\text{In}_x\text{Ga}_{1-x}\text{Sb}$).

Results. A new analytical expression is derived for calculating the temperature dependence of the oscillations of the transverse electrical conductivity and magnetoresistance of a quantum well. A mechanism has been developed for the oscillation of the transverse electrical conductivity and magnetoresistance of a quantum well from the first-order derivative of the magnetic field (differential $\frac{\partial(\rho_{\perp}^{2d}(E, B, T, d))}{\partial B}$) at low temperatures and weak magnetic fields.

Conclusion. Oscillations of the electrical conductivity and magnetoresistance of a narrow-window quantum well with a nonparabolic dispersion law are studied. The proposed theory was used to study the results of experiments on a narrow-gap quantum well ($\text{In}_x\text{Ga}_{1-x}\text{Sb}$). The Landau levels of the $\text{In}_x\text{Ga}_{1-x}\text{Sb}$ quantum well in weak magnetic fields, which were not observed in the experiment, oscillate. This has been proven through the $\frac{\partial(\rho_{\perp}^{2d}(E, B, T, d))}{\partial B}$ theory of magnetoresistance. The experiment shows that the oscillations of the transverse magnetoresistance of the $\text{In}_x\text{Ga}_{1-x}\text{Sb}$ quantum filament, measured at a temperature of 2 K, transform into a continuous energy spectrum due to thermal washing under the influence of the temperature growth dynamics.

Keywords: semiconductor, magneto-optical absorption coefficient; Landau levels; oscillations of the combined density of states; modeling; pressures; temperatures.

Introduction. As is known, the influence of external factors (temperature, magnetic field and pressure) on quantum-dimensional heterostructures leads to a change in the position of the energy levels of charge carriers and, consequently, to a shift of the magneto-optical absorption edge[1-20]. The magneto-optical absorption spectrum of nanoscale semiconductors is determined by the energy distance between different minima of the sparse zone. Hence, the width of the

forbidden zone of the quantum well can either decrease or increase due to external influences. Thus, the study of the magneto-optical absorption spectrum near the boundary of its absorption edge provides information about the structure of the energy spectrum of charge carriers near the lower edge of the conduction band and near the upper edge of the valence band of the quantum well, which is essential for determining the magnetic, optical and

electrical properties of nanoscale semiconductors.

The combined densities of quantum well states play an important role in the oscillation of interband magneto-optical absorption. Therefore, in many cases, the matrix element (p_{cv}) changes little within the Brillouin zone.

Consequently, the structure of the spectrum mainly determines the combined density of states in quantum-dimensional heterostructures. In works [1-3], a method was developed for calculating the oscillation of the combined density of states in a quantizing magnetic field with a non-quadratic law of dispersion under the influence of temperature and hydrostatic pressure. This method is used in the study of magnetic absorption in narrow-band semiconductors with a nonparabolic dispersion law. A fan diagram of the magnetic absorption spectrum in narrow-band semiconductors is constructed. However, these papers do not consider the temperature dependence of the two-dimensional combined density of states in the allowed zone of a quantum well with a parabolic law of dispersion. That is, the resulting method is applicable only for bulk semiconductor materials.

In addition, in works [4,5], the spectrum of InGaN/AlGaIn/GaN heterostructures with quantum wells is emitted by an LED and analyzed on the basis of a two-dimensional combined density of states model. The considered model of approximation of the luminescence spectra of LEDs in these works was developed for complex heterostructures with multiple quantum wells. In work [6], a random walk in a two-dimensional space consisting of an energy

parameter of the order and an energy correlation function was performed, and a two-dimensional combined density of quantum well states was obtained. The order parameter, susceptibility and correlation function are calculated from the two-dimensional combined density of quantum well states. Numerical calculations of the author show that for the purposes of determining the two-dimensional combined density of states in continuous models, the Wang–Landau transition matrix method can be considered as an alternative to the pure Wang-Landau method. In work [7], an exact mathematical expression is proposed that directly combines the density functions of the states of the resolved zone of a quantum well to create a two-dimensional combined density of states for direct transitions. Using both expressions, the absorption coefficient of the quantum well and the superlattice was calculated, which led to a positive coincidence with the experimental data. In the above literature, the temperature dependence of the oscillation of the two-dimensional combined density of quantum well states in a quantizing magnetic field is not discussed. Also, the work determines the oscillations of the combined density of quantum well states at constant temperatures in the absence of a magnetic field.

Methods. The purpose of this work is to determine the effect of a strong magnetic field on the combined density of states in heterostructures with quantum wells.

In the absence of a magnetic field, the dependence of the density of the energy states of the conduction band and the valence band in the quantum well on the energy spectrum of charge carriers are step functions (Fig.1a) [21]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 g_c(E) &= \frac{m_n^e}{\hbar^2 \pi} \sum_n \theta(E - E_n) \\
 g_v(E) &= \frac{m_n^h}{\hbar^2 \pi} \sum_m \theta(E - E_m)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

Here, m_n^e and m_n^h are the effective masses of electrons and holes in the dimensional quantization subband in a quantum well numbered n and m . $\theta(E)$ - Heaviside step function.

For direct interband transitions, the combined densities of states are a convolution in energy, which also has a step function in energy [21]:

$$N_{jds}^{2d}(E) = \frac{m_{mn}^*}{\hbar^2 \pi} \sum_{m,n} \theta(E - E_{mn}) \quad (2)$$

Here, m_{mn}^* is the reduced effective mass of charge carriers for the subzones of dimensional quantization n and m , which is calculated by the ratio: $(m_{mn}^*)^{-1} = (m_n^e)^{-1} + (m_m^h)^{-1}$.

Fig.1. The energy distribution of the density of electronic states in quantum-dimensional GeSi/Si structures [21]: a - quantum well, b - quantum dot

If the electronic and hole states in GeSi structures turn out to be size-quantized in all three quasi-momentum components, that is, they represent a quantum dot for charge carriers, then in this case the combined density of states in the allowed band of such a structure is a Gaussian function (Fig. 1b). Then, in the allowed zone there is a zero-dimensional combined density of states, which is a discrete non-decreasing function. In this case, the combined density of states is described using the so-called Dirac delta function $\delta(E)$:

$$N_{jds}^{0d}(E) = \sum_{l,m,n} \delta(E - E_{lmn}) \quad (3)$$

The combined density of states is a collection of infinitely narrow and high peaks (Fig.1b). All the results obtained above are valid for cases without the influence of quantization of the magnetic field, temperature and pressure. Specific questions arise: how to determine the combined density of states in quantum-dimensional direct transitions of

heterostructures in the presence of a strong magnetic field? How does the dynamics of temperature rise affect this process?

Let's calculate the dependence of the combined density of states on the quantizing magnetic field in two-dimensional semiconductor materials with direct allowed transitions. In a quantizing magnetic field, the combined density of states is defined as an integral over all states in the conduction band with energies E_C and in the valence band with energies E_V of the quantum well, which satisfy the law of conservation of energy during the magneto-optical transition. Let us analyze the simplest model of a band structure near the edge of the band gap of a straight-band heterostructure with a quantum well under the influence of a strong magnetic field. That is, the valence band of the quantum well is completely filled with charge carriers, and the conduction band is empty. Here, the filling functions of the corresponding states are equal to $f_V=1$, $f_C=0$. In addition, in this model, the